

Research on the Collaborative Development of Regional New Quality Productivity by Government, Universities, and Enterprises

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Abstract: New quality productivity emphasizes the integration of technological innovation resources, with emerging strategic industries and future industries as carriers, and technological innovation talents as support. It has three significant characteristics: innovation, integration, and digitization. In the context of the national construction strategy in the new era, new value co creation and collaborative interaction relationships have been formed among governments, universities, and enterprises in the region. This article analyzes and discusses the coordinated development of regional new quality productivity, examines the actual problems between the government, universities, and enterprises, and explores the strategies for strengthening the transformation of scientific and technological achievements and promoting high-quality collaborative interaction in empowering new quality productivity. The article believes that in the new era, the coordinated development of regional new quality productive forces should follow the following principles: regional governments need to build a clear system of coordinated development systems with clear rights and responsibilities; The development direction of universities should match the actual needs of the region; Enterprises should strengthen their main responsibility for participating in collaborative development from a high starting point. Only by fully leveraging their own advantages and forming a close cooperation mechanism can we promote the sustained and healthy development of local economy and society, achieve regional economic prosperity and social progress.

Keywords: New Quality Productivity; Region; Government, Universities and Enterprises; Coordinated Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the two sessions in China, General Secretary Xi Jinping delivered a series of important speeches on developing new quality productive forces, improving strategic capacity in emerging fields, and deepening reform. They scientifically answered a series of major questions concerning the long-term development of the cause of the Party and the country, and were highly political, ideological, theoretical, strategic and guiding. In the work report of the government made by Premier Li Qiang made comprehensive arrangements for the work of the whole year, including a series of arrangements for improving the socialist system of socialism with Chinese characteristics, deepening the reform and upgrading of regional reform, optimizing the layout and structural adjustment of the state-owned economy, which fully reflected the great importance the CPC Central Committee and The State Council attach to regional development [1]. This is a historic period of convergence between a new round of scientific and technological revolution and industrial transformation and China's transformation of its development model. China is facing both a golden historical opportunity and a severe challenge facing

a widening gap. The new quality productive forces is a new qualitative state of productive forces formed and developed under such a historical background, and the decisive role in realizing the new historic leap of productive forces is increasingly prominent.

General Secretary Xi Jinping stressed: "All localities should proceed from reality, adapt measures to local conditions, guide the development of new industries, new models and new drivers, selectively promote local resource endowment, industrial foundation and new research conditions, transform and upgrade traditional industries with new technologies, and actively promote high-end, intelligent and green industries." The methodology and requirements for development are put forward. This marks the completion of a cycle from the gestation, proposal, establishment, deepening to the implementation of new quality productivity, that is to say, the end to the previous stage. After the two sessions, China has entered the stage of comprehensive implementation of [2]. The formation of new quality productivity cannot be separated from the support of science and technology, but also inseparable from the guidance of innovation. General Secretary Xi Jinping once clearly pointed out that "development is the top priority, talent is the first resource, and innovation is the first driving force". "Education, science and technology, and talent are the basic and strategic support for building a modern socialist country in an all-round way" [3]. The development of regional scientific and technological innovation involves two main bodies of industrial system and education system. It is the key node for the deep integration of innovation chain, industrial chain, capital chain and talent chain, and plays a decisive role in the formation of new quality productive forces.

Over the years, China has made remarkable achievements in the transformation of its scientific and technological achievements. However, as the central and local governments have introduced innovation incentive policy, production with project and public service platform subsidies and a series of measures, we should also see that industrial system in scale is large but strength is yet to be enhanced, comprehensive but not fine problems still exist, especially the regional development has a lot of the space to ascend. This is mainly due to the fact that most participants are too much about the maximization of their own interests, some subjects have a unclear understanding of the actual situation, the actual ability of the scientific research achievements transformation is limited, and the transformation approval process is cumbersome. At the same time, the synergy between market-driven, government guidance, capital support and bridging platforms still needs to be improved.

2. THE VALUE OF REGIONAL NEW QUALITY PRODUCTIVITY

In the process of promoting the progress of regional productivity, collaborative development plays a key role in promoting the level of regional technological innovation [4]. This promotion is not only the inherent requirement of the development of regional productivity, but also a necessary condition for its sustainable and healthy development [5]. The core of collaborative development lies in the comprehensive integration of the advantages of regional administrative mechanism, education system and industrial system. This integration is not a simple physical superposition, but based on the basis of deep cooperation and chemical reaction to achieve the synergistic effect of $1 + 1 + 1 > 3$. Therefore, the collaborative mode formed by this resource integration has become the core driving force to promote the high-quality development of regional new quality productivity.

The coordinated development of the government, universities and enterprises is of great significance for promoting resource sharing and realizing complementary advantages. Through in-depth cooperation, all parties have formed a strong synergy in innovation, technology, talent and other fields to jointly enhance their overall competitiveness. At the same time, this coordinated development helps to promote the integration process of industry, university and research, accelerate the transformation and application of scientific and technological achievements, and inject new impetus into regional economic development. In addition, it also helps to cultivate innovative talents, provide a solid talent guarantee for regional economic and social development, and provide strong support for the realization of comprehensive, coordinated and sustainable development of regional economy and society.

The Function of Regional New Quality Productivity and High-Quality Coordinated Development of Government

The role of regional government in University-enterprise cooperation and regional economic development promoted by industry, university and research institutes is no longer only "rowers", that is, only relying on administrative means to promote cooperation [8]. On the contrary, it needs to become a "helmsman". While making the overall planning of University-enterprise cooperation within the administrative region, it also needs to improve the undertaking capacity of the market, expand the market demand, realize the connection between supply and demand, broaden the path of participation,

and enrich the means of governance, so as to lay a solid governance foundation for the development of new quality productive forces in the region.

The development of the new productive forces is the key role of the government, and the application of the new productive forces is particularly important. In this context, the coordinated development model of Chinese government, University and enterprises has experienced the transformation and upgrading from simple University-enterprise cooperation to closer integration of industry and education [7]. This transformation means that universities and enterprises are no longer just one-way cooperation, but coordinated by the government to form a community of shared future.

The Function of Regional New Quality Productivity and High-Quality Coordinated Development of Universities

The scale and development structure of higher education are the key factors that determine the development level of human capital in a region. Human capital, as the most fundamental factor to promote the development of productivity, has an extremely strong explanatory power for economic growth. At the same time, the contribution of universities in scientific research has undoubtedly played a positive role in promoting the development of regional economy. In addition, in terms of infrastructure construction, the government, enterprises and society [9]; the cultural ideas and values of universities will also affect the adjustment of economic growth mode to some extent; in the basic theory research of emerging industries, the promotion of regional productivity.

Regional development also significantly promotes the improvement of college education quality. For Universities, the improvement of education level needs certain support from the regional government. In areas with rapid development of public education and rapid economic development, higher education generally gets more support. The more developed the regional economy is, the more support the government gives to higher education, and usually improves the financial expenditure of public education to support the accelerated development of [10]. It can be concluded that the development of Universities and the regional economic structure and development are closely linked and complementary. We must attach great importance to the important position of higher education in regional development, and give full play to its positive role in promoting economic growth, improving the level of human capital, and promoting scientific research and innovation.

The Function of Regional New Quality Productivity and High-Quality Coordinated Development of Enterprise

As an important participant in coordinated development, enterprises should carry out the further optimization of funds, personnel, facilities and other resources on the basis of following the government's regional coordinated development strategy, major strategies and main functional zone strategy, and combine the reasonable allocation of personnel training teachers, funds, practical resources and other factors. Only in this way can we build a community of common destiny between government, Universitys and enterprises based on talent training, technological innovation as the core, social service as the link, employment and entrepreneurship as the platform, and cultural inheritance as the soul.

In the background of promoting new quality productivity in the new era, we should not only pay attention to the training of innovative technical personnel, but also ensure the close connection with cutting-edge technology, industrial development needs and regional economic development direction, so as to provide a powerful power source for the leap-forward development of regional economy [11]. By deepening scientific research cooperation and optimizing the talent structure, we will continuously improve the regional innovation capacity, promote industrial transformation and upgrading, and lay a solid foundation for the sustainable development of the regional economy. In this process, enterprises should play the role of the main force in the development of new quality productive forces, and provide solid support and guarantee for the strategic implementation of the government and universities.

To sum up, in order to jointly promote the improvement of regional new quality productivity, the internal connection between the government, universities and enterprises is crucial. In the transformation of scientific and technological achievements, as the main force of scientific research, universities are the main position for knowledge innovation and training scientific and technological talents in the early stage of transformation, and as the carrier of transformation of scientific and technological achievements, the industry is also the home place for the practice of scientific and technological achievements and give full play to the talents of talents. The realization of the value of scientific and technological achievements can further promote the development of the industry, and the development of the industry will produce the demand for innovation of knowledge. In this way, the cooperation between universities and industries will be increasingly deepened. In the transformation of science and technology, the government plays a large role, such as relationship

coordination, docking leading, division of responsibilities, etc., so as to ensure the effective flow of knowledge in the external environment [12]. It can be concluded that in the transformation of scientific and technological achievements, the main responsibility of universities is to create knowledge and carry out research and development work. Distribution of human resources; the main responsibility of the government is to formulate and improve the corresponding policies and systems, guide and supervise the transformation process; the main responsibility of the enterprise is to provide financial support for universities and governments and provide places for the transformation of scientific and technological innovation achievements. In the practical transformation of scientific and technological achievements in Universities, the government, universities and enterprises fulfill their responsibilities and cooperate with each other, so as to lay a solid foundation for the sustainable and healthy development of new quality productivity in the region.

3. THE CURRENT PRACTICAL PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED

Driven by the wave of digital intelligence, China's regional innovation capacity has been continuously improved, and the deep integration of industrial chain and innovation chain has injected new vitality into the national innovation system, and provided a steady stream of power for accelerating the formation of new quality productivity [13]. Although China has entered the stage of high-quality development and the pace of industrial transformation and upgrading is accelerating, there is still a significant gap between the efficiency of the transformation of scientific and technological achievements and the demand for the deep integration of industry and education. In order to make up for this gap, it is particularly important to improve the efficiency and strength of the transformation of scientific and technological achievements. It is not only a bridge connecting the supply side of talents and the demand side of enterprises, but also the key to promote the integration and utilization of digital intelligent scientific and technological resources and accelerate the training of new quality talents. In the current context, we are faced with several important problems that need to be solved urgently:

The Dilemma of Power and Responsibility in the Transformation of Scientific and Technological Achievements Is Increasingly Emerging

First, there is a deviation problem in the concept of regional government responsibilities. Exercising powers and performing duties in accordance with the law is an important responsibility of regional governments to promote advanced productive forces and improve the efficiency of the transformation of scientific and technological achievements. The correct exercise of power is of great practical significance to enabling high-quality development. To further improve and perfect the legal system for the transformation of scientific and technological achievements is to explore an effective transformation way suitable for the development of education, society and economic development. In the transformation of scientific and technological achievements, the definition of rights and responsibilities and the scope of regional governments can be allowed to have certain ambiguity under the influence of the continuous optimization of government functions and powers. However, in the public and private law domain, the necessary boundaries must be clarified to reflect the different [14] attributes of the two fields. However, the definition and scope of regional government powers and responsibilities and their scope have not been clarified in the current relevant legal system, which leads to the unclear scope of functions, the increased difficulty of power operation, and the lack of effective response of the responsible subjects of public affairs. These problems lead to the phenomenon that the regional government functions are confused with the blank of responsibilities.

Second, the current conflict resolution mechanism has obvious deficiencies in the process of transformation of scientific and technological achievements. For regional governments, the scope of their rights and responsibilities in this process is not only unclear in relevant laws and regulations, but also not stipulated in relevant normative documents. Therefore, all government departments cannot perform their duties and have no provisions. For the transformation of scientific and technological achievements affairs, even if the local government of the relevant laws and documents in the responsible functional departments, but these provisions are often too general, the lack of specific operation, so a lot of the time is regarded as the principle, resulting in the transformation of scientific and technological achievements activities lack of effective guidance, also for the relevant government departments to implement authority offside behavior provides a certain space. In addition, there are intersections and conflicts in normative documents in various fields. Effective communication and coordination in the transformation of scientific and technological achievements are needed to make these regulations play a role. However, no efficient communication mechanism has been established, which makes such coordination difficult. In order to solve these problems, it is necessary to further improve the conflict resolution mechanism, clarify the scope of the powers and responsibilities of various functional departments, and strengthen the communication and coordination between departments to ensure the smooth transformation of scientific and technological achievements.

Third, there are serious defects in the supervision and evaluation mechanism of regional governments in the process of scientific and technological achievements. As the main body of public power, the regional government assumes the important responsibility of supervision and evaluation in the process of the transformation of scientific and technological achievements. However, due to the lack of clear, scientific evaluation criteria, the practice of regional government in the exercise of supervision and evaluation power face larger discretion, and evaluation results and performance of government workers plays a decisive role, so, the evaluation result is easy to be tampered with or false, thus affect its objectivity and authenticity, and weaken the role of supervision and evaluation, so that both the adjustment of the direction of adverse effect, also to the sustainable development of the activities. Therefore, we must improve the supervision and evaluation mechanism of regional governments to ensure the smooth progress of the transformation of scientific and technological achievements.

The current system of Universities does not match with the industrial development direction in the region

First, Universities pay attention to theoretical education and laying the foundation, and enterprises pursue practicality and benefits. The update of the university talent training program is not closely combined with the current needs of enterprises, especially if there is a significant mismatch between the curriculum design and the real workplace demand. According to Michael's report, in the past five years, there has been no significant improvement in the evaluation of core courses related to their majors. In the class of 2022, up to 59% thought that practice and practice were insufficient, and 36% thought that the course content was less practical or too outdated [15]. However, there are many challenges to addressing this problem. At present, the training programs of most Universities are still based on the relevant requirements of the National Standards for Teaching Quality of Undergraduate Majors in Regular Institutions of Higher Learning (2018). Although revised every four years in principle, [16] is only optimized in part according to the demand in other years. Although China higher education institute has introduced production innovation standards, and expect Universities to promote the university-institute cooperation, but in practice, by the traditional academic concept and teachers, the adjustment of college training program space is limited, lead to the obvious gap between the industry demand, the broad masses of students with exam-oriented education mode of thinking into the university, no curiosity, accustomed to be instilled knowledge rather than active learning. Therefore, there is an obvious disconnect between the current university training program and the employment needs of enterprises.

Second, the current degree of integration of university majors and regional key industries and emerging industries is still insufficient. When planning the industrial layout, the local government fails to closely combine the dominant disciplines of universities in the region, leading to the failure of the regional industrial chain to fully cover the dominant discipline chain of universities. In addition, in the process of participating in high-level talent training, enterprises are faced with the problem of rapid talent loss, which not only extends the benefit cycle of talent training, but also increases the cost of enterprises investing in simulated industrial scene equipment. At the same time, the lack of relevant policy support also restricts the sustainable development of the industry. At present, there is still a mismatch between the education supply side and the demand side in the transformation of scientific and technological achievements. Therefore, it has become an inevitable trend to promote the development of new quality productivity and enable the transformation of the government, reverse the situation of one-way drive in education, realize the coordinated cultivation of reserve talents and promote the transformation of internal driving energy.

Third, the evaluation and evaluation mechanism of Universities urgently needs to be improved. In Universities, the current evaluation system, the scientific research evaluation, the core position, and teaching evaluation, the evaluation system, although also included in the achievements transformation evaluation, but in the marginalized, lead to the transformation of Universities is not enough attention, even often ignore, coupled with the transformation of scientific and technological achievements, Universities lack of sufficient professional professional managers to support the scientific and technological achievements team, the research team achievements and management generally lack of professional knowledge, and lead to achievements facing difficulties, also makes the enthusiasm of the research and development team by a blow. Therefore, the barriers in the process of scientific and technological achievements in Universities still pose a great obstacle to the integration of innovation resources.

In The Process Of Enterprises Participating In The Transformation of Scientific and Technological Achievements

First, in the coordinated development of government, University and enterprises, the key link for enterprises to participate in the goal of cooperation. However, the main obstacle is that it is difficult to achieve net income. When discussing the purpose of the company's joining activities, we should rethink the basic intention of economic activities, including "profit-

driven" and "profit-driven", and consider the balance of cost and benefit and other major factors. Although the social responsibility activities such as talent training are not their direct economic responsibility, the costs and benefits brought by these activities will eventually be included in the company's economic accounting. After detailed research, it is found that the fundamental purpose of the company's participation in cooperative development is the growth of net income (profit) [16]. However, at present, many enterprises, in the process of actually participating in the coordinated development, still have doubts about whether they can achieve the goal of increasing the net income. This doubt is the fundamental reason for the "enthusiasm" and "indifference" attitude in the coordinated development of government, University and enterprises. In order to promote the smooth coordinated development of government, University and enterprises, we need to pay attention to and solve the problem of net income faced by enterprises in the collaborative cooperation. Only by ensuring that enterprises can obtain real economic benefits in participating in the coordinated development can they be stimulated to participate more actively and actively in this process.

Second, the participation methods and links of enterprises in the cooperation, and their problems are mainly reflected in the balance of responsibilities and rights. In the process of enterprises' participation in the transformation of scientific and technological achievements, the word "participation" clarifies the supporting role and assisting status of enterprises in relevant activities, and their corresponding responsibilities, rights and obligations have obvious participation attributes, which indicates that the company usually cannot have complete control in the decision-making of key matters. If companies cross this line, partnerships may risk disruption. After research, how to define the resource advantages, responsibilities and rights of enterprises and Universities in the process of transformation of scientific and technological achievements and whether their goals are consistent are the key factors affecting the process and depth of university-enterprise cooperation, and also determine the breadth and depth of enterprise participation. The imbalance of responsibilities and rights is the main limitation and root cause that enterprises do not actively participate in cooperation.

Third, in the process of participating in collaborative cooperation, enterprises are mainly faced with difficulties in the implementation of systems and mechanisms. In cooperation, enterprises usually through the transformation of scientific and technological achievements as a link, closely combined with the University. There are three ways of participation, mainly including: the experiment of the mechanism layer, the discussion of the system layer, and the combination of innovation in the system and the mechanism. There are various forms of cooperation between enterprises, which can choose sole proprietorship, cooperation, joint venture and other ways to carry out business. In addition, entrustment management and service purchase and other models are also effective means to achieve cooperation. At the same time, enterprises can adopt mixed ownership, joint-stock system and other ways, through the deep integration of capital, management and technology, and cooperation with Universities to establish productive training bases. After 20 years of development, China's higher education institutions have successfully developed cooperation models such as "industry and education integration" and "industry and education integration" based on the University-enterprise cooperation system. Nevertheless, the close combination of this model and institutional innovation is very insufficient. In order to achieve the goals of "industry-education integration ecosystem" and "industry-education integration community construction" corresponding to the shareholding system and mixed ownership, the specific operation is still facing great difficulty. In the process of realizing the coordinated development of the three parties, the institutional obstacles of insufficient participation of enterprises have become the core problem and urgent task restricting the high-quality development of new quality productive forces.

4. KEY PRINCIPLES OF COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT

The proposal of new quality productive forces has opened up a new development path and injected new vitality into the socialist modernization drive with Chinese characteristics. In order to promote the synergistic progress of new quality productivity and the government, universities and enterprises, we can start from three levels. First of all, we should form synergy, the government should be active, Universities should have the courage to innovate, the market should operate effectively, and jointly optimize the development path of productivity. Secondly, the priority for practical results, adhere to the problem-solving oriented, to meet the service needs as the goal of [17]. Finally, to achieve sustainable development, which is in line with China's new development concept, and to jointly create advanced productive forces in line with local characteristics. Accelerating the improvement of new quality regional productivity will provide solid regional support for the socialist modernization drive with Chinese characteristics. In view of the roles and functions of the government, universities and enterprises in high-quality development, we need to follow the following development principles:

Adhere To the Concise Characteristics and Connotation of the Development Is the Direction of the Development of New Quality Productive Forces

Characteristic concise and connotative development are interrelated and mutually promoted, which together constitute an important part of regional collaborative innovation development. The characteristic concise is the key premise and core requirement to promote the realization of the connotative development, and the connotative development is the value and final destination of the characteristic concise. Through characteristic refinement and connotative development, the comprehensive strength of government, University and enterprise cross-integration can be effectively enhanced, so as to attract more external resources and promote regional innovation and development.

Specifically, characteristic concise and connotative development needs from the following aspects: first, to clarify the regional collaborative innovation development of strategic positioning and development direction, find the intersection between the colleges and fusion point, to ensure that collaborative innovation can form a solid structure, avoid disconnect phenomenon, foster new regional economic growth point at the same time. Secondly, it is necessary to consolidate the foundation, strengthen the advantages, give full play to the advantages of government, Universities and enterprises in their respective fields, realize complementary advantages and resource sharing, and promote the improvement of regional development level. Finally, it is necessary to form characteristics, establish brands, avoid blindly follow the trend and image projects, and ensure the sustainable development of collaborative innovation.

In the process of promoting the characteristic concise and connotative development, the government, universities and enterprises need to make joint efforts. Enterprises should be guided by the development of new quality productive forces, improve their own research and development capabilities and innovation capabilities, strengthen cooperation with universities, and promote the transformation of scientific and technological achievements. The government should provide strong support for the cooperation between enterprises and universities, including institutional guarantee and policy guidance, and to promote the close connection between scientific and technological achievements and practical applications. At the same time, it is also necessary to promote the virtuous cycle mode of coordinated development of government, Universitys and enterprises through the combination of internal and external incentives, so as to ensure that the cultivation of new quality productivity can be promoted smoothly and orderly.

In short, the characteristic concise and connotative development is an important way to promote the regional collaborative innovation development, which requires the concerted efforts of the government, universities and enterprises to contribute to the realization of the sustainable and healthy development of the regional economy.

Adhering To Problem Solving and Service Demand Orientation Is a Strong Guarantee for the Development of New Quality Productive Forces

As for the layout adjustment of regional new quality productivity, in addition to the optimization and combination of conventional geographical structure, more attention should be paid to the improvement and promotion of functional level. This means that we must improve the ability to upgrade the service industry, and adhere to the problem-oriented, actively respond to service needs, which is of great significance for promoting regional development. The party's 20th plan clearly put forward the overall planning and integrated deployment of education, science and technology and talents, which fully demonstrates the party and the country's deep understanding and grasp of the characteristics and development trend of high-tech industries.

In order to meet the needs of industrial innovation in the new era, the government, universities and enterprises must form a close coordinated development relationship. On the one hand, the basic theoretical research in universities plays an irreplaceable role in solving major social problems and promoting breakthrough development. Through the close contact with the society, we can win the wide recognition and trust of the society, so as to attract more outstanding talents and resources together. The innovation and development, on the other hand, the region must closely track the technology, closely around the national development strategy, aiming at the core technology and key applications, to clear discipline development direction, concise regional characteristics, grasp the key, scarcity resources, and national stable "strategic" relationship, get more financial support and legitimacy recognition.

Therefore, to promote the development of regional new quality productive forces, it is necessary to have a forward-looking, overall and strategic vision, but also to establish a sense of service and exploration spirit. We must attach importance to

academic research, but also pay attention to social needs, and strive to make substantial and original contributions to the national and social development. This is not only an inherent requirement for new quality productivity to enable high-quality development, but also an important guarantee to attract the attention and support of external resources.

Strengthening the Incubation of Entity Enterprises Is the Sustainable Carrier of the Development of New Quality Productivity

The core of the continuous collaborative innovation of regional new quality productivity is to improve the self-development and hematopoietic ability. For Universities, the key to innovation lies in closely combining with local needs and taking innovation and entrepreneurship projects as the carrier to realize the deep integration and coordinated development of academic and industrial circles. Through the establishment of business incubators, to promote the rapid transformation of research and development results to industrialization, and then create a positive cycle. Industrial enterprises should provide timely and strong support for research and development innovation by means of shares, achievement transformation fees and research funds.

In the value-added activities such as providing technical services, managing patents, incubating enterprises and making equity investment, universities can obtain economic benefits through the commercialization of scientific and technological achievements, which can support the sustainable development of universities, so as to achieve the effect of self-regeneration of funds. At the same time, it should also stimulate the enthusiasm of researchers for innovation, and allow them to hold intellectual property rights and team shares, so as to further stimulate their innovation vitality.

Through the establishment of industrial base, attract small and medium-sized enterprises to use the equipment and venues of universities to jointly carry out research and development and incubation. It can further promote the close integration of industry, university, research and application. However, the current industrial parks established by universities generally fail to realize the incubation needs of innovative enterprises, and few financial service institutions provide angel investment or venture capital support for enterprises in the start-up stage in the park.

Therefore, the government should continue to improve the financial policies, increase the supply of investment, set up a reasonable risk compensation system, and increase the policy support for enterprises closely combined with industry, university, research and application. Innovation in Universities should closely combine with regional needs, actively build new research and development institutions, and promote the development of related disciplines and innovation and entrepreneurship. Resident universities should attach great importance to the development of new research and development institutions, and give strong support and discipline integration.

In particular, application-oriented universities should focus on their own strong disciplines, transform academic achievements into easy-to-understand productive forces, transform industrial demand into scientific research orientation, and realize the deep integration of scientific research and industry. Through the co-construction and sharing of multiple resources, including scientific research literature, courseware, instruments and other scientific and technological resources, by promoting the clustering of industries, focusing on centralized research and development and the complementary advantages of resources, it aims to achieve economies of scale, and further strengthen and expand the market competitiveness of independent innovative enterprises.

5. PRACTICAL STRATEGIES FOR COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT

It is a systematic and complex task for the government, universities and enterprises to cultivate new quality productivity. It is necessary to establish a sound innovation coordination mechanism, improve the collaborative system and optimize the collaborative structure, so as to effectively promote the high-quality development and the steady improvement of regional construction. In order to ensure the smooth coordinated development of regional productivity with the government, universities and enterprises, the following practical strategies are put forward:

Regional Governments Need To Build a Coordinated Development System with Clear Rights and Responsibilities

First, regional governments should actively promote the effective implementation of administrative regulations and departmental regulations for coordinated development. Within the framework of the current legal system, the formulation and improvement of administrative regulations and departmental regulations closely related to collaborative progress should be rapidly promoted to establish a set of legal system that meets the needs of education and social and economic

development [18]. This will not only ensure that local governments have laws to follow when promoting the development of emerging productive forces, but also reflect the important role of the rule of law in regional coordinated development. Through this series of laws and regulations construction, for the regional coordinated development of the smooth promotion of providing a solid legal guarantee.

Second, we will strengthen administrative norms to ensure that the "last mile" of institutional supply for coordinated development is unimpeded. Administrative normative documents of regional governments play a key role in the implementation of the coordinated development system, which is directly related to the implementation effect and development direction of the coordinated development legal system. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that the local administrative norms conform to the responsibilities of regional governments, and their powers and responsibilities are consistent, and then further clarify the scope of government functions, so as to ensure that the regional coordinated development affairs can be effectively implemented, and provide clear operational guidelines.

Third, improve the joint supervision and evaluation system of regional governments and industry associations. We should make full use of the resources, platforms and information advantages of industry associations in the process of common development, so that they can play the role of bridge and link among the participants, so as to effectively promote the circulation of information and resources, steadily promote the talent exchange between Universities and enterprises, and achieve the optimal allocation of resources. To be precise, industry associations should provide professional assistance such as technical guidance, platform services and data support for activities carried out by Universities and enterprises to ensure that their collaborative activities can be carried out with high quality and high standards. In addition, with the help of its mature service system and standardized internal organizational structure, it provides theoretical support for the regulatory evaluation activities of local governments.

The Development Direction of Universities Should Match With the Actual Regional Needs

First, strengthen the cooperation and innovation between the region and universities, take the common concept and the integrated culture as the cornerstone, and realize the mutual empowerment and coordinated development of both sides. Universities should actively integrate the regional elements, clarify the target positioning, optimize the specialty Settings, innovate the University-running mode, closely combine the local specific needs of higher education and the evaluation system, and strengthen the insight and understanding of the local culture and innovation needs. In addition, Universities need to take advantage of their regional characteristics and challenges to transform them into a source of power to promote their own educational development and provide intellectual support for regional economic development. Through this move, it can not only enhance the economic strength of the region, but also enhance the government's ability to undertake the "spillover effect" of universities, so as to realize the benign interaction between education and economy.

Second, in the process of promoting regional development, it is necessary to respect and guarantee the autonomy of Universities in innovative running Universities. While strengthening top-level design and overall planning, Universities should be endowed with suggestions and supervision in regional development. For the innovation and development of both regions and universities, a multi-dimensional and multi-level stereoscopic governance network should be established. By improving the communication and coordination mechanism, ensure the effective connection and interaction of all stakeholders in the top-level design and strategic planning. In view of the transformation of scientific and technological innovation achievements, we should focus on original, leading and forward-looking science and technology, focus on tackling key problems, and strive to achieve landmark breakthroughs in major key projects. A sustainable and complementary institutional framework should be constructed to eliminate the organizational boundaries and knowledge barriers between the government, universities and enterprises, so as to promote the synergy of collaboration and linkage.

Three is about the coordination of scientific and technological innovation, must fully mobilize the government, universities, enterprises and the social from all walks of life participation enthusiasm and the main body responsibility, jointly promote the vigorous development of new technology, new methods, new tools and innovative vitality, for the birth of emerging industries and traditional industry upgrade into a steady stream of power, so as to effectively promote the cultivation and development of new productivity. Based on the actual needs of regional development, we should maximize the advantages of the universities in scientific research and actively explore the potential of basic research and the transformation of scientific and technological achievements, the advantages of regional industries should be used to promote the entry of innovative achievements with potential commercial value into the market, so as to achieve the commercialization and mass

production of scientific and technological achievements of [19]. Closely combine the knowledge chain and industrial chain, establish a strategic cooperation platform integrating industry, university and research, create an ecological chain of industry-university-research integration innovation in line with the regional characteristics, and provide solid support for the sustainable and healthy development of regional economy.

Enterprises should strengthen the main responsibility of participating in the coordinated development from a high starting point

First, with the continuous advancement of the globalization trend and the increasingly fierce market competition, enterprises play an increasingly critical role in the process of promoting regional coordinated development. As the core participants in economic activities, enterprises should not only pay attention to the improvement of their own economic benefits, but also take the initiative to assume social responsibilities, and strengthen their main role in regional coordinated development with high standards and strict requirements, so as to make positive contributions to the promotion of regional economic integration.

Second, in terms of strengthening the main responsibility, enterprises should adhere to the development concept of win-win cooperation, and actively integrate into the deep integration strategy under the leadership of the regional government. Enterprises and universities should deepen the integration of industry and education, and jointly build University-enterprise cooperative units with the basic characteristics of production plants by increasing cooperation. These cooperative units should fully reflect the needs of production practice in the physical space and organizational form. In addition, the implementation scope of University-enterprise cooperation should include practical education, innovation and entrepreneurship, technical support, social organization training, industrial incubation and other fields, so as to build a comprehensive system integrating education and practice. In terms of ownership and asset structure, the units participating in the cooperation should implement the mixed ownership model of combining state-owned capital and private capital, and ensure that both parties can achieve the goals of joint construction, mutual benefit and mutual sharing in terms of internal management and achievement sharing.

Third, Universities and enterprises should be on the basis of mixed ownership joint construction unit, actively carry out produced talents, institutions, research cooperation, resource sharing and other diversified cooperation projects, these measures can promote the effective docking between talent training and demand, through the innovation of organization and service mode, so as to promote the quality of talent training [20]. At the same time, a high starting point to strengthen the main responsibility of participating in coordinated development is an important guarantee for enterprises to achieve high-quality development in the context of new quality productivity. Therefore, enterprises should actively embrace the reform, bravely shoulder the mission of The Times, contribute greater strength to promote the coordinated development of regional economy and society, and show their social responsibility and responsibility.

6. CONCLUSION

It is an important measure to promote the development of new regional productive forces and to promote the sustainable and healthy development of regional economy and society. The government has the power of policy formulation and resource allocation, universities have rich scientific research resources and talent reserve, and enterprises, as the main body of the market economy, have the ability to transform scientific research results into productive forces. Therefore, the close cooperation and synergy of the three will form a strong development force.

The government should formulate scientific and reasonable policies to provide solid support and guidance for the cooperation between universities and enterprises. Through financial input, tax incentives, project support and other means, universities and enterprises are encouraged to carry out in-depth cooperation, and promote the transformation and application of scientific research results. At the same time, the government also needs to strengthen market supervision, ensure fair competition, and create a good market environment for both sides.

Universities should give full play to their own scientific research resources and talent advantages to provide technical support and talent training for enterprises. Through close cooperation with enterprises, jointly carry out scientific research projects to promote the transformation and application of scientific research results. In addition, the teaching mode and curriculum system connected with the development of industrial enterprises should be established to provide enterprises with high-quality human resources and help enterprises in technological innovation and industrial upgrading.

Enterprises should actively participate in the cooperation between universities and the government, make full use of the technology and talent resources of universities, and promote their own technological innovation and industrial upgrading. Through in-depth cooperation with universities, explore the collision and discussion of new technologies and new ideas, and improve the production efficiency and product quality of enterprises. At the same time, enterprises can also cultivate their own reserve talent team through cooperation with universities, to lay a solid foundation for sustainable development in the future.

To sum up, when the government, universities and enterprises cooperate to jointly promote the development of new regional productive forces, all parties need to give full play to their own advantages and form a close cooperation mechanism. Only in this way can we promote the sustainable and healthy development of local economy and society, and realize the prosperity of regional economy and social progress.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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